

Religio-nationalism and ‘soft boundaries’: Urban gating in West Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

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ABSTRACT

Recent scholarship on gated communities has challenged assumptions about the homogeneity of aesthetics and motivations for enclosure, emphasizing the place-bound origins and meanings attached to exclusionary development. It has also called for a conceptual shift in classifying gated communities from the ‘hard’ boundaries of a gate or wall to more ‘soft’ boundaries that achieve a similar outcome of limited or discouraged access. In this article, we examine urban luxury gated communities in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv to demonstrate three main points. First, we explore how the unique and vastly different socioeconomic contexts and built characters of Jerusalem and Tel Aviv influence the aesthetics, marketing techniques, and residents of their respective gated communities. Second, we demonstrate how ideological and neoliberal interests have converged in new luxury gated communities, while emphasizing the diverse manifestations of exclusionary development within a single country. Third, luxury gated communities in downtown Jerusalem and Tel Aviv illustrate the need to shift attention away from an increasingly outdated notion of ‘hard’ gatedness towards accounting for the diversity and range of ‘soft boundaries’ that enclose and serve to privatize space while relying upon and perpetuating both local and national social and economic polarization.

1. Introduction

In the past two decades, a great deal of scholarly attention, especially in the fields of geography, urban sociology, and economics, has been directed towards the examination of structural forces that propel the growth of gated communities globally, as well as their diverse social impacts and physical manifestations at the local level. Despite the global ubiquity of gated communities, and although gated and exclusionary development in diverse locales may share systematic or root causes, they should not be understood as a unitary occurrence (Pow, 2015; Rosen and Razin, 2009; Grant and Mittelsteadt, 2004). Gated communities respond to the context of certain organizing social and political structures and dynamics. Additionally, considered as a real estate or architectural product, the production of gated communities is subject to the influences of place-bound notions of prestige, safety, and elite aesthetics in cultivating an attractive image of lifestyles ‘behind the gates’ (Low, 2003). The political aims and cultural norms that condition the proliferation of gated communities are especially dynamic and instructive in the case of Israel, a socially and economically diverse country that has developed rapidly, albeit unevenly and controversially, since its establishment in 1948. The various religious,

ethnic, political, and economic cleavages that characterize Israeli society are engendered in gated communities and types of gatedness that are ripe for theoretical analysis.

Like countless other cities around the world, Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, the two most populous cities in Israel, have in recent years experienced a construction boom in luxury residential communities, including closed condominiums (Santos Cruz and Pinho, 2009) and gated developments, primarily in their respective city centers (Alfasi and Ganan, 2015; Margalit, 2014, 2013). These ‘new gated communities’ (Rosen and Razin, 2008, 2009) share with their international counterparts many structural economic drivers, yet also depart from the typical form in many significant ways. Most notably, they are influenced by conditions unique to Israel, such as those related to its central ethno-national role for much of world Jewry, its highly polarized socioeconomic structure, and the Israeli-Palestinian geopolitical conflict, and are located in the urban core, as opposed to the suburban or rural periphery (Rosen and Razin, 2008, 2009). On the city-level scale, the various ways in which exclusive developments in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv have been designed and marketed reveal that the two cities are subject to different social forces and constraints, manifest globalization in divergent ways, and represent various political forces in the country.

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The local ‘gating machines’ and ‘gating coalitions’ (Vesselinov, Cazessus and Falk, 2007) of the two cities—a constellation of interests surrounding planning codes and practices, developers and real estate agents, and socio-cultural conditions including consumer tastes and expectations—propel gated development nationally, but also produce important distinctions. Jerusalem bears an important nationalist, geopolitical, and religious significance and is segregated along Jewish-Arab and religious-secular lines, while Tel Aviv is a ‘modernized’ global financial center and staunchly secular metropolis, where economic polarization and ethnic segregation are reflected in the urban social structure. While much work has shown how national histories and conditions shape the production of gated communities (Leisch, 2002; Kuppinger, 2004; Salcedo and Torres, 2004), little attention has been paid to how politically-charged religio-national goals can be advanced by city-specific gated developments.

Our research seeks to fill this gap by examining how economic conditions and prevailing political goals in Israel have resulted in the construction of aesthetically varied luxury residential complexes in its two largest cities. Also, although not physically surrounded by gates, we argue they still function in a manner similar to the archetypal, easily distinguishable gated community typology (Rosen and Walks, 2015b; Shahar, 2012). This paper, then, seeks to characterize diverse means of enclosure in gated development, encompassing the prototypical hard boundaries as well as more novel ‘soft boundaries’, across the case studies of Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, signifying an under-examined form of spatial exclusion in the contemporary urban landscape in which neoliberalism and religio-nationalism converge.

The paper is divided into three sections. First, we contextualize this research within the current state of the literature on gatedness and exclusionary urbanism globally and in Israel. Second, we highlight a convergence of neoliberalism and a state-level religio-nationalism in the development of luxury compounds in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, associating each city’s cultural conditions with different constructions of Jewish heritage and Zionist identity. Related to recent work on the ‘reinvention’ of the kibbutz that conceptualizes an integration of different interests (notably Charney and Palgi, 2018), we argue that ideological and neoliberal interests are similarly merged in new luxury gated communities, but in an urban, rather than rural, context. Finally, we critically analyze the developments’ various mechanisms of exclusion and modes of gatedness, encompassing individual design features and spatial patterns regarding their built surroundings. The research is based on qualitative fieldwork conducted in the winter of 2015–16, including interviews with key actors and local field observation, and a range of pertinent academic, governmental, and promotional resources.

While we argue that the gated developments reflect the cities’ disparate built histories, they both variously cement a relationship between neoliberal housing development in Israel and the broader political situation, in which a more profound gatedness pervades and motivates political aims and ideology. This research reinforces how city-level socioeconomic dynamics and national political goals converge to influence the production of gated communities and demonstrates the diverse manifestations of exclusionary development within a single country. We argue for a shift in attention away from an increasingly outdated notion of ‘hard’ gatedness towards a deeper understanding of the diversity and range of ‘soft boundaries’ that enclose and serve to privatize space while relying upon and perpetuating social and economic polarization in the regionally ‘gated’ context of Israel.

2. Gated communities: origins and forms

2.1. A global phenomenon

A large and growing body of scholarship responds to the increasingly prominent role gated communities have played in urban and residential development in the last two decades. The literature on gated communities is widely thought to have been jumpstarted with Blakely

and Snyder’s groundbreaking 1997 study of the growth of gated enclaves in the United States (Vesselinov, 2010), which theorized the impacts on community, citizenship, and local socioeconomic rifts if an ever-increasing share of citizens were ‘retreating from their neighbors by locking themselves behind security-controlled walls, gates, and barriers’ (Blakely and Snyder, 1997: front flap). The research that followed has emphasized theoretical concerns regarding ‘spatial fragmentation, social exclusion, citizenship and democracy’ (Landman, 2004: 151), seeking to illuminate the broader political and economic contexts within which social segregation and gated communities arise, but generally eschewing discussion of physical and design features (Grant and Mittelsteadt, 2004; Ruiiu, 2014).

2.2. Theoretical drivers of gated development

Gated residential development has been commonly conceptualized as an extreme manifestation and result of gradual societal trends towards social polarization, urban fragmentation, and economic segregation (Kovacs and Hegedus, 2014; Ruiiu, 2014; Mycoo, 2006). Many scholars have shown, in a wide variety of contexts, how gated community development represents an ultimate, if not inevitable, form of segregation based on local ethnic and socioeconomic cleavages and inequalities (Zhao, 2013; Vesselinov, 2012). Scholars have sought to understand how the development, marketing, and popular representation of gated communities are conditioned by, and further perpetuate, local social hierarchies and exclusionary practices (Gadecki and Smigiel, 2013). Importantly, gated communities have been especially rooted in metropolitan-level causes, leaving the relationship between luxury development, neoliberalism, and state-level political intent under-examined. We believe this domain is productively investigated in highly fraught and fractured countries such as Israel.

The rise of gatedness has been largely attributed to fears of crime, prompting wealthy elites to withdraw from public life and isolate themselves within the enclaves, akin to Blakely and Snyder’s (1997) ‘security zones’. The role of crime, or the perception of it, figures prominently in the gated community literature as catalysts for ‘fortress’-style development (Landman and Schonteich, 2002; Low, 1997, 2003). In contrast to this fear- and security-based explanation for gatedness, some scholars have shown how a desire for an elite lifestyle and a high level of prestige, especially in the developing world, drives a great deal of gated development (Mycoo, 2006; Leisch, 2002). Still others seek to tease out whether the underlying reasons for gatedness are based more on a desire for security or for prestige (Csefalvay, 2011; Kovacs and Hegedus, 2014).

These two broad streams of thought in the literature, which Kovacs and Hegedus (2014) name the market- and politics-driven approaches, both assign the greatest importance to actual or symbolic security to account for the popularity and widespread production of gated communities, although for very different reasons. The market-based approach considers security an exclusive and consumable commodity that is increasingly being guaranteed at the neighborhood-level under neoliberal forms of governance, while the politics-driven approach links socio-spatial segregation and an elite—supposedly unfounded—fear of crime in explaining the enhanced desire for ‘security.’ These two approaches to explaining the proliferation of gated communities globally bear important consequences. While the market-based notion emphasizes neoliberal economics and governmental *retreat* in generating segregation and inequality, the politics-based approach explains the roots of such social ills by ascribing more sinister intentions, often related to advancing historical inequities and institutional racism, resulting in enclaves that become symbols of social polarization and group conflict.

Lastly, an important theme in the literature emphasizes the roles of local municipal structures and neoliberal governance in facilitating the development of gated communities (Rosen and Razin, 2008, 2009; Tedong et al., 2015), determining their locations and spatial contexts

(Libertun de Duren, 2006), and enabling the privatization of public space and resources (Le Goix and Webster, 2006; Thompson, 2013). Such studies, which can generally be associated with the market-driven approach, employ a neoliberal framework to understand how economic-political conditions such as budgetary shortfalls, mass privatization of public space and services, and a disproportionately empowered economic elite all serve to help produce gated enclaves.

2.3. The ‘glocality’ and the ubiquity of gatedness

Despite the salience of globalizing and structural considerations in the literature, a growing number of scholars have expressed concern over the theoretical oversimplification of the drivers behind local gated development (Pow, 2015; Webster, Glasze and Frantz, 2002; Rosen and Razin, 2009), suggesting that more attention should be paid to the ‘indigenous innovations contributing to the local phenomena [and] the institutional, social, economic and cultural contexts in which gated communities are emerging in [disparate parts of] the world’ (Webster, Glasze and Frantz, 2002: 316). In order to more comprehensively understand the causes and contexts of the production of gated communities, then, we must dispose of the assumption that drivers of gated developments are uniform between (or among) countries and regions, and rather investigate how the ‘global urban form has been transplanted and translated into the city’s landscape’ (Genis, 2007: 771), and how they, simultaneously, ‘articulate global models and local realities’ (Kuppinger, 2004: 36). Examining the combination of both global and local factors that shape gated development is especially relevant in the Israeli case, where Jerusalem and Tel Aviv are thought to represent competing sets of national values and poles of identity (Alfasi and Fenster, 2005).

Furthermore, beyond emphasizing the impact of local conditions on the adapted global form of urban gating, researchers in recent years have called for an expansion of what is considered ‘gated’ and ‘enclosed’ (Yip, 2012), directing attention towards the subtle and ‘soft boundaries’ of gatedness (Bagaean and Uduku, 2015; Havermans and Smeets, 2010) that constitute geographies of exclusion. In the book *Beyond Gated Communities*, for example, the authors propose a shift ‘beyond the traditional terminology of the gated community – fixed in history, location and urban-architectural typology’ (Bagaean and Uduku, 2015: 3) to a focus on ‘urban gating’, i.e. a shift from the familiar notion of the hard edges of the self-contained gated community to the more fluid, sometimes softer boundaries’ (Bagaean and Uduku, 2015: 9). This new perspective sees gated communities as encompassing a range of physical and symbolic barriers and various other means of exclusion, which results in non-traditional, dynamic and ‘layered’ forms of gatedness and enclosure in the context of urban fragmentation and social detachment (Alaily-Mattar, 2008).

More specifically, scholars have examined how inner-city luxury towers represent a new form of exclusionary space and gated community that is not ‘always or necessarily included among the traditional definitions of gating, but which function in a very similar fashion’ (Rosen and Walks, 2015b: 155; Graham, 2015; Shahar, 2012). This type of inner-city development reflects recent trends in metropolitan development away from suburban and exurban expansion towards ‘downtown intensification’ and densification (Rosen and Walks, 2015b: 156). According to Graham (2015: 628), this ‘elite takeover of the urban skies’ constitutes a vertical form of gatedness, and ‘now rivals their more familiar horizontal shift to gated suburban, exurban or resort enclaves.’

2.4. Exclusionary development in urban Israel

North American-style gated communities in Israel first emerged in and around Tel Aviv in the 1990s, reflecting a growing ‘demand for lifestyle, prestige, and privacy by individuals’ (Rosen and Razin, 2008: 2907). However, Israel has had a long history of ethnic segregation and

inequality reproduced in the built landscape, as well as of politically or religiously-propelled enclave development, namely West Bank settlements. Therefore, contrasted with earlier forms of Israeli gatedness (such as that of *moshavim*, cooperative settlements, and *kibbutzim*, collective agricultural settlements), the new ‘neoliberal gated developments’ (Rosen and Razin, 2008) are characterized by profit motivations, a lack of public intervention, and desire for elite status markers.

Some empirical studies have examined various forms of exclusive Israeli urbanism with respect to national social patterns and inequalities. Three social cleavages form the basis for inequality and exclusion in Israeli society: national, religious, and ethnic (Schnell and Benjamini, 2004). The national division between Jews and Palestinian Arabs is the most divisive, as it constitutes the basis of the decades-old, intractable Israeli-Palestinian conflict. The religious cleavage, between secular and religious or ultra-Orthodox Jews (*haredi*), and the ethnic cleavage, between Jews of European descent (*Ashkenazim*) and those of Asian or North African descent (*Mizrahim*), also shape Israel’s socioeconomic structure and hierarchy (Yiftachel, 2000; Schnell and Benjamini, 2004). With respect to the national divide in Israeli society, Falah (1996) has examined Arab-Jewish ‘hypersegregation’ in several ‘mixed’ (Jewish and Arab) Israeli cities, finding a sectorial pattern of residential differentiation and attributing it to various hierarchies that become concretized spatially.

Critical scholars have associated these inequalities with an ‘ethnic logic’ of Judaization and Jewish indigenization, or the nationalist project of inscribing and expanding Jewish identity on the land (Yiftachel, 1999; Yacobi, 2002). Additionally, the dominant Ashkenazi/subordinate Mizrahi divide, forming the basis of economic and residential segregation in Jewish Israeli cities, is also examined extensively in the literature (Shoshana and Samimian-Darash, 2014; Schnell and Benjamini, 2004; Khazzoom, 2003). Many critical scholars have identified the central Israeli government with policies of ‘engineering’ (intra-Jewish) ethnic segregation through, among other means, its immigrant integration policies (Tzfadia, 2006; Khazzoom, 2005; Yiftachel, 2000). Others have detected, especially in Jerusalem, political motives and symbolic meaning embedded in civic projects and residential development (Rosen and Charney, 2016).

Critical research, closely associated with the work of Erez Tzfadia, Oren Yiftachel, and Haim Yacobi, among others, ‘emphasizes the central role of the government establishment, national institutions and ideologies in walling out and exclusionary practices’ (Tzfadia, 2005: 141), which embody and facilitate the Zionist aim of Jewish settlement of the biblical Land of Israel. While this critical, neo-colonial perspective emerged among Israeli academics in describing segregation decades ago, the subject of Western-style, ‘neoliberal’ gated communities in Israel did not receive scholarly attention until recently. Rosen and Razin’s (2008, 2009) research distinguishes these new lifestyle-oriented privatized residential compounds from more politically-rooted enclosed communities. Yet few scholars have associated the Israeli government with seemingly ‘neoliberal’ (and therefore free from government direction) dynamics, such as gated development. Consistent with other literature that emphasizes status and prestige in motivating enclosure, Rosen and Razin (2009: 1718) also argue that ‘the new gated communities are predominantly a product of market mechanisms, representing class-based segregation rather than ideology, ethnic identity or security considerations.’ This conclusion theorizes a convergence of market mechanisms and a top-down ‘ethnic logic’ in producing segregated landscapes (Tzfadia, 2005; Yacobi, 2012a), yet differs from the neo-colonial critical perspective in that it argues that market forces supersede state-led demographic engineering. In contrast, Monterescu’s (2015) work on luxury gated enclaves in Jaffa has highlighted the state-led nature of the national and ethnic power imbalances that underpin exclusive urban development in Israeli cities, while assigning a secondary role to neoliberal economic considerations in perpetuating inequalities.

Few studies have addressed the more current and relevant form of

gatedness in Israel—the proliferation of luxury residential development in its metropolitan areas—and how they illustrate the convergence of neoliberalism and Israeli political-demographic aims. Alfasi and Ganan (2015) examine the recent spread across West Jerusalem of exclusive luxury condominiums geared towards wealthy diaspora Jews as vacation or part-time residences, and stress the prominent role of heritage projects and foreign direct investment in producing this form of private, urban gated community. Yacobi (2012a, 2012b) explores the mass privatization of inner city West Jerusalem through exclusive residential development and unpacks the ethnic and religious power structures embedded in the design and marketing of the gated communities. Through a survey of the residents of 15 luxury residential towers in Tel Aviv, Shahar (2012) argues that they function as gated communities, due to their shared amenities ('club goods'), the role of 'security' in attracting residents, and residents' relatively weak connections to the surrounding neighborhood. In our research, we seek to build on the scholarship on enclosed, exclusive development in metropolitan Israel and suggest that in Israeli gated communities neoliberalism coalesces with religio-national political goals. However, due to the cities' vastly different social structures and religious and political significance, we demonstrate how a religio-national logic is stronger in Jerusalem than in Tel-Aviv and manifests differently in urban gating strategies.

3. Neoliberalism meets religio-nationalism in luxury urban gating

3.1. Jerusalem: selling an ethno-national 'home'

Consistent with the city's important religious and national status, Jerusalem's gated developments seek to cultivate a sense of Jewish history and heritage, selling its role as the spiritual capital of a national homeland and central site of Zionism. Furthermore, Jerusalem's role as a national frontier that continues to expand into Palestinian territory to the east injects the city's real estate with an important nationalist and geo-political dimension and introduces a new meaning and scale of 'gatedness' in this unique context. The tourism function of Jerusalem is important, and, due to its frontier status, is especially imbued with religious and geopolitical significance. Historically, municipal and national authorities have established sites across the city 'with an emphasis being placed on the development of those with an Israeli and Jewish orientation, so as to amplify the Israeli nature' (Shoval and Cohen-Hattab, 2001: 922), indicating a state-led effort to deploy the hospitality and foreign-accommodation industry as a political tool.

As discussed by a number of researchers recently, the national government and the Jerusalem municipality in particular have embarked upon a plan to fill the city's increasingly wide budgetary shortfalls by enticing wealthy Jews from North America and Europe to its housing market via tax benefits (Alfasi and Ganan, 2015; Yacobi, 2012a), while seeking to establish politically and strategically favorable demographics. These new Western-origin residents spend little time out of the year in the luxury homes, leading to their deprecating appellation 'ghost complexes'. As the project manager of one inner-city luxury complex said, 'most people spend about two months per year here, a week here, a week there. Some of them [even] make short-term rentals' (personal communication, 2015). More importantly, they utilize little to no municipal services, and contribute foreign direct investment (FDI) funds to the strained tax base of the municipality. This scenario is considered a win-win for both the migrants and the Jerusalem municipality, if not for the several inner-city neighborhoods that lay mostly vacant throughout the year (Haramati and Hananel, 2016). Only recently has this been recognized as a problem that is exacerbating the severely strained housing market (Mayor of Jerusalem, 2009).

The desire of Jerusalem's luxury developers to attract these wealthy Jewish immigrant-visitors is evident particularly in the developments' marketing campaigns. Advertisements for developments are frequently taken out in American, British, and French newspapers, and deals are often made with local real estate agents that specialize in foreign

buyers. Importantly, a majority of these Western immigrants to Jerusalem are religious; Jerusalem receives more religious immigrants from the West than any other city in Israel (Zaban, 2017). As pointed out by Yacobi (2011), immigration and settlement in Jerusalem bear a unique character from settlement in other parts of the country, due to the city's national religious centrality and its frontier character as a site of constant Israeli expansion into Palestinian territory. Therefore, the attractiveness of certain developments as presented in promotional material is couched in terms of religious and spiritual considerations, a sense of Jewish ethno-national belonging unique to Jerusalem, and appeals to the history of Jewish Jerusalem, all of which is often cast through orientalist imagery and an orientalist lens.

The Hanevi'im Boutique development, for example, is clear in its targeting of religious, foreign Jews for marketing campaigns. Its promotional video depicts aerial views of the highly contested Old City overlaid with audio of the traditional Jewish song *Im Eshkacheh Yerushalym* ('If I shall forget thee, O Jerusalem'), as a yarmulke-wearing resident of the project describes Jerusalem as 'my home away from home. Jerusalem is in the heart of every Jew, religious and non-religious.' The website for David's Village plainly states, 'this luxury complex was especially built for wealthy overseas residents, and includes a 24-hour security service' (David's Village, n.d.).

One project developer discussed the idea that the luxury developments of Jerusalem are targeted *exclusively* to wealthy Jews from abroad:

My boss is a *haredi* [ultra-Orthodox Jew], and everybody who buys here needs to be Jewish. Because it is a rule in the *Gemara* [Oral Tradition], that if you sell an apartment in Israel, the buyer needs to be Jewish... It's very hard to explain this to a non-Jew, that we cannot sell to non-Jewish people. It's a *halacha* [Jewish law], but you can do whatever you want. Most of the people coming here are from abroad, most of the people who live here are from abroad. They are all Jews, not *haredi*, but not *hiloni* (secular). *Dati* (observant). (personal communication, 2015)

Although this 'Jews only' policy is somewhat unique to the circumstances behind this particular development, it reveals the extent to which ethnicity and religion play prominent roles in the population of these projects. Additionally, the developer confirmed there are no Israeli nationals living in the development, as 'it's very expensive for them...between 2.6 million shekel and it goes up to 8 million shekels [about \$665,000 to \$2 million US dollars]' (personal communication, 2015).

Luxury developers seek to 'sell' both historic and modern Jewish Jerusalem (Yacobi, 2012a), locating their projects within a historicized, orientalized atmosphere of the city while providing modern and luxurious amenities. The promotional video for the Hanevi'im 45 complex is an example of this trend. The complex is presented as towering over its historic built surroundings, yet in harmony with the architectural styles that dominate the neighborhood. Shots of the sleek edges of the tower are juxtaposed with close-ups of Jerusalem-style archways, gardens, and porticoes. The main lobby is even shown to house a single Middle East-style wall of arched windows built of 'Jerusalem stone'¹ while close-ups of the gym, sprawling dining rooms, and outdoor balconies confirm it is still a modern architectural creation (Hanevi'im 45, 2012). Similarly, the architect for Hanevi'im Boutique is featured in a promotional video, saying, 'I tried to emphasize the merging of old and new. The glass, steel and stone come together, while the typical arch only shows up in specific places.' The websites for two developments insist residents participate in 'Jerusalem's past, present and future' (King David's Crown, 2013).

Certain design features and services further demonstrate that they

¹ A project manager of one development explained that they were legally obligated to build using materials reminiscent of historical Jerusalem.

are developed with religious Jews in mind. The complexes advertise outdoor balconies that are suitable for the building of a *sukkah*, the traditional hut temporarily erected for the holiday of Sukkoth, an especially popular time among Orthodox diaspora Jews for visiting Israel. All of the developments under examination in Jerusalem have ‘Shabbat elevators’ that can be used by observant Jews without violating the Sabbath.² Some projects even include synagogues within the complex boundaries.

Finally, the naming of the developments as a marketing tool itself constitutes additional evidence of the religious and cultural connotations strategically attached to the projects. King David, ancient king of Israel and generally perceived among Jewish communities as a great builder of Jerusalem, is frequently referenced in the developments’ names, such as King David’s Crown and King David’s Residence, to further a sense of cultural legitimacy and authenticity. The projects Jerusalem of Gold and Jerusalem Gold Garden evoke an image of luxury and opulence, which is concurrently a nod to the traditional Jewish perception of Jerusalem as built from gold. Furthermore, the names of developments also signify the relative safety of a district: ‘What [a name] tells the investors, when it’s ‘King David’, is that it’s under a safe area, in a good area...because it is in the Jewish area’ (personal communication, 2015). The branding of some developments also reinforces this association. For example, the logo of Jerusalem of Gold is a lion, symbolic of Jerusalem, and 7 Kook’s is a harp, suggestive of King David’s musical prowess. These promotional aspects of the luxury developments collectively serve to project an image of Jerusalem that aligns with Western-conceived and orientalized ‘imagined geographies of the city’ (Yacobi, 2012b: 67), in order to best attract potential buyers while discursively associating the historic land with modern Israel.

In summary, Jerusalem’s luxury residential developments are designed, marketed, and discursively framed as a spiritual, emotional, and ethno-national ‘home’ for wealthy Jewish immigrants who wish to purchase real estate in the Jewish-defined and strategically significant city—an enterprise shrouded in Zionist political meaning and implication. The luxury communities represent a governmental attempt—from tax incentives to harnessing and perpetuating popularized images of the holy city—to attract Jewish transnational elites, in order to grow municipal tax revenues, promote a positive image of Jerusalem and Israel broadly, and engineer demographics that reinforce the status of Jerusalem as capital of Israel, marking a convergence of profit-seeking market mechanisms and Israel’s ethno-national and strategic goals. The locus of Jerusalem’s gated nature and controversial expansion into Palestinian territory, then, should not only be located at the scale of municipal boundaries (Yacobi, 2012b), but also at individual sites, such as gated and luxury communities, dotting Jerusalem’s urban landscape, constituting its frontier character, and perpetuating its status as the heart of a more religious and conflict-ridden brand of Zionism.

3.2. Tel Aviv: local elites, global orientation

In contrast to Jerusalem, Tel Aviv is a modern, secular, and globally-oriented city, evident in its social atmosphere, politics, and built forms (Avni et al., forthcoming; Marom, 2014; Alfasi and Fenster, 2005). Forming the economic and cultural hub of Israel and its largest metropolitan area, Tel Aviv is characterized by a generally higher socio-economic status, although national and ethnic inequalities and residential segregation still suffuse the urban landscape (Omer and Goldblatt, 2012). Beginning in the 1990s, Tel Aviv was increasingly associated with the global, post-industrial economy (Kellerman, 1993; Kipnis, 1997), due to its international financial links, role as a service

and command center, and intensive research and development capabilities. Yet Tel Aviv is unique among global cities in that it does not, due to antagonistic regional geopolitics, ‘enjoy multiple cross-border activities with its neighbors’ (Kipnis, 2004: 186)—a dead-end or *cul de sac* spatial condition—and its global-city status was earned ‘in spite of its frontier location in its region’ (Kipnis, 2004). Although it is often presented as outside the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, Tel Aviv is nonetheless conditioned by a geopolitical situation and embodies a version of the Zionist dream, albeit a more modern and globalized one that is influenced by European-style urbanism and ideology. Concentrated especially in the neighborhoods north of the downtown core, historically home to wealthy veteran Ashkenazi families, a construction boom in luxury high-rise condominiums has drastically changed the city’s physical and social fabric (Margalit, 2013). This section discusses the design, marketing, and socio-cultural characteristics of these luxury developments, and their role within broader issues of neoliberal economics and politics.

Local history and a sense of ethno-national heritage are notably absent as selling points in Tel Aviv’s luxury complexes. Rather, exploiting the wealthy and global character of the city, the developments are presented as a private and prestigious dream home for Israel’s business, cultural, and political elite. All of the developments under present analysis offer a private pool, spa and fitness center, as well as 24/7 security, and concierge service. Many also offer exclusive ‘residents’ clubs’ or gardens. Depicted as islands of calm within a commercially and culturally bustling city, the projects enable residents to view their urban surroundings without experiencing them. The 1 Rothschild project, for example,

offers residents an intimate and tranquil refuge from the bustling surroundings...The building has attracted many members of Israel’s business, industrial and cultural elite...Each apartment, ranging in size from 190 to 1,200 sqm, is equipped with balconies and 3.15-meter floor-to-ceiling windows, enabling residents to take in the spectacular surroundings. (Habas, n.d.; emphasis added)

Savyoney Ramat Aviv, a fully-enclosed private neighborhood in the secluded northern reaches of the city, is advertised in a promotional video as, ‘our private island...an island of activity and an island of serenity; an island of relaxation, and an island of fulfillment...our home, for us. It’s an island of harmony’ (AFI Group, n.d.). Privacy and prestige are therefore prominent themes in the marketing of the complexes. Residents are able to indulge fully in the varied urban offerings of Tel Aviv, while preserving the ability to retreat into their towering high-rises or gated compounds and ‘leave the city outside’ (Home Land Realty, 2009).

In contrast to Jerusalem’s luxury compounds, where historical surroundings, orientalist imagery, and proximity to religious sites are touted most prominently, the marketing of Tel Aviv’s luxury towers highlights architectural designs, individual ‘starchitects’, and a ‘world class’ aesthetic. In the case of Rothschild 1, ‘the 32-floor glass and steel tower exudes the quiet chic of a unique masterpiece...an artful composition of contemporary luxury and perpetual elegance’ (Habas, n.d.). The YOO complex in Park Tzameret, which was ‘inspired’ by renowned architect Philippe Starck, ‘sets a new global standard for lavish living’ and is said to ‘reflect Starck’s four signature palettes’ (Habas, 2017). The Meier on Rothschild is even named for its chief architect, Richard Meier, and features changing art installations (Rosenblum, 2013). Tel Aviv’s luxury developments are therefore marketed as more than mere homes or lifestyle complexes—they are unique architectural and artistic products for a cosmopolitan elite. Indeed, the slogan of the G (or Ha-Shoftim) Tower is ‘The Art of Living.’

Tel Aviv’s luxury residential projects are generally designed in an ultra-modern, placeless, globalized style. Nearly all of the developments under discussion are built of a concrete and steel frame, with glass and aluminum or steel facades. With the exception of the Savyoney Ramat Aviv enclosed complex, all the projects are towers that range from 26

² Shabbat elevators stop on every floor of a building automatically, and do not require the user to press any buttons, enabling Orthodox Jews to ride an elevator on the Sabbath without violating the prohibition on using electricity.

stories (G Tower) to 46 stories (W Tower in Park Tzameret). While some developments may claim to emulate or adapt to the surrounding International Style structures (commonly known as Bauhaus) that typify Tel Aviv's architecture, simple observation of the finished products reveal that they are quite distinct from those styles' characteristic designs, and rather bear a placelessness that may be considered interchangeable with similar projects across Asia and the Middle East. Developments in Tel Aviv emphasize the city's international links, influences, and reputation within the Israeli and global urban systems. The projects' short, stylized names in English, such as YOO, NAM, ONE, further demonstrate that they have a global orientation and are used to assert an international, cosmopolitan reputation for the city (and, in turn, the country).

The Tel Aviv developments are geared towards Israel's (largely) Jewish business and cultural elite, and a clientele more secular than that of Jerusalem. A real estate agent at Home Land Park Tzameret, a central agency for the towers in the exclusive neighborhood, pointed out that the buildings had a variety of residents in terms of family status, but was almost entirely Jewish and secular (personal communication, 2015). The lack of balconies suitable for the building of a *sukkah*, which were available in nearly every unit in Jerusalem's developments, illustrates this relative secularity. In fact, the website for the gated Savoyney Ramat Aviv complex boasts that the neighborhood is '76% secular.' *Shahar* (2012) surveyed 96 residents of luxury and 'ordinary' residential towers in Tel Aviv, and found similar trends. The luxury towers contained significantly higher shares of young (25–35), divorced, widowed, and single homeowners than those of the ordinary towers and only four residents (9%) listed their degree of religiosity as 'religious' or 'very religious.' Additionally, the real estate agent at Park Tzameret stated that the majority of the neighborhood's residents were Israeli citizens, as opposed to foreigners or part-timers. *Shahar* (2012) confirms this, finding that three quarters (74.4%) of luxury tower residents in his sample were born in Israel. Needless to say, the projects have few or no Muslim Arab or non-Jewish residents.

Significantly, although Tel Aviv is less reliant on foreign religious buyers and the selling of an imagined, orientalized cityscape as in the case of Jerusalem, it nonetheless represents an alternative vision for the Israeli/Zionist city, and is thus riddled with geo-political meaning. Tel Aviv's economic prowess and global cultural import advances broader goals of the Israeli state by presenting a modern, secular front that masks urban and social dynamics more visible in Jerusalem. In this sense, although its relationship to globalization is significantly more economic and nominally less politicized than in the case of Jerusalem, Tel Aviv merges—and simultaneously addresses—the interests of economic neoliberal and Zionist ideologies of Jewish cultural production, both strategic interests of the Israeli state.

4. 'Soft boundaries': urban gating in Israel

Jerusalem's and Tel Aviv's luxury residential developments employ a patchwork of what scholars refer to as 'soft boundaries', in addition to the familiar 'hard boundaries', in delineating and appropriating space, a process that can be compared with more typical 'horizontal' gated communities as examined in recent scholarship. While most of the complexes under consideration use site-specific spatial properties and 'soft boundaries' to isolate residents, some projects, most explicitly Savoyney Ramat Aviv, are completely enclosed and restrict all non-resident access. In this section, we discuss the range of techniques of spatial differentiation and enclosure that isolate Israel's inner city luxury compounds from their urban environs, transforming them from mere exclusive developments into defensible gated communities.

All of Jerusalem's developments analyzed here claim to offer 24/7 supervised and guarded entry, as well as individual unit CCTV and intercom systems. Some go even further: King David's Crown, for example, offers residents 'a designed high-security door, and aluminum windows with isolating glass.' The Meier on the Rothschild

development describes its level of security as follows:

Our residents' security comes first. The Meier on Rothschild luxury tower was designed precisely to ensure their ultimate seclusion and privacy. With these planning principles in mind, the entrance to the lobby area is private and restricted, exclusive to residents and invitation only guests and guarded with a 24-hour doorman. (*Berggruen Residential Ltd., 2016*)

The developer of a project located off the Ben Yehuda Street pedestrian mall and tourist zone justified a high level of security:

It's better for the clients. When you are from abroad, like Americans, if something small happens [i.e. a terrorist attack or flare up in tensions], they don't want to come anymore. They are afraid. (personal communication, 2015)

Providing security systems and an image of fortification, therefore, is a matter of good business and economic sense. Residents wish to separate and protect themselves from the perceived risks associated with the geopolitical conflict that deflect Israeli life, in addition to ordinary urban crime.

The sheer height and massing of the buildings in both Jerusalem and Tel Aviv is an important means of exclusion, making them into isolated spaces that are infrequently navigated. Indeed, one pedestrian outside the G Tower in Tel Aviv said the development is incongruous with its surroundings, which are of substantially lower scale, and that it should not be considered as inviting because it 'doesn't fit in at all' (personal communication, 2015).

Many of the developments with internal gardens that are technically public discourage public access through suggestive design measures and the formation of boundaries. Dark underpasses, plant installations, security booths, (unlocked) metal gates, aggressive signs about acceptable behavior, CCTV cameras, and waist-level traffic-cone fixtures, for example, introduce artificial boundaries and function to deter access into legally public space (Fig. 1). A common feature of entrepreneurial urban development—the preservation of a public park or historical structure—is often used as a *de facto* means of limiting access and facilitating spatial isolation (*Alfasi and Ganan, 2015*). In the case of King David's Crown in Jerusalem, the developers were required to build and maintain a 1.25 acre central courtyard as a public park. However, it is almost entirely closed off from outside streets with only a few discrete and unmarked entrances that are intentionally easy to miss.

The Akirov Towers, a set of three nearly identical 34-story residential buildings in Tel Aviv, harnesses its siting to deploy many 'soft' boundaries and measures to restrict non-resident access. Located on a slightly higher elevation than the street toward which it faces, the structures tower over street-level pedestrians (requiring the negotiation of either a ramp or a set of steps) and are further recessed behind meandering paths and gardens. Finally, waist-level walls that contain Akirov's 'public' gardens are topped with pointed metal triangles that prevent sitting. This design decision clearly demonstrates an effort to prevent the space from ever being utilized or perceived as accessible to the general public.

The placement or orientation of a development in terms of its surrounding spatial configuration and street structure can also serve to isolate and differentiate it from adjoining public space (*Omer and Goldblatt, 2012*). Park Tzameret in northern Tel Aviv is a particularly illustrative case. Nestled within three major thoroughfares, the complex of 12 high-rise buildings can be seen as a neighborhood unto itself, as it is completely unintegrated with the surrounding urban space. On its west side, the complex is separated from the rest of Tel Aviv by a high wall and a major traffic artery with a grassy median and two bicycle lanes. It is bound on its east by the Ayalon Highway and River. Within, a mixture of public and private spaces renders the entire enclave alienating to anyone wandering through its single road and ostensibly public central shopping mall. Similarly, developments such as Jerusalem's 7 Kook and King David Residence are surrounded on the

Fig. 1. A range of soft and hard boundaries enclose luxury developments in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv. Clockwise, from top left: Metal spikes at the Akirov Towers; Guard booths in David's Village, downtown Jerusalem, discourage access; the fully enclosed Savyoney Ramat Aviv complex; fences and explicit signage at King David Gardens.

Source: Authors.

ground level by arcades of luxury boutiques and services catering to wealthy Jewish tourists. By transforming the area into a privatized zone of consumption, the development may further deter 'undesirables' via more subtle means. Considered holistically, the spatial and locational contexts of the developments function to separate them from urban space.

As mentioned above, despite the proliferation of 'soft' boundaries due to the political and aesthetic unpopularity of more extreme, disruptive, and discernible means of exclusion, it is important to note that some projects do employ physical fences and explicit signage to exclude non-residents. King David Gardens, for example, is cut off from surrounding central Jerusalem by a series of fences and shrubs with signs reading 'Private Property – No Access' in both English and Hebrew. Savyoney Ramat Aviv in Tel Aviv is completely enclosed by the complex's ten buildings, automated garage doors, terraced walls, and two guarded entrances.

In sum, through a patchwork of hard and 'soft' boundaries often inhabiting the same spaces, involving both contextual siting and specific design implementations, central Jerusalem and Tel Aviv have been transformed into 'a privatized frontier' (Yacobi, 2012a), increasingly oriented towards wealthy and consumptive Jewish residents. Ranging from Savyoney's impenetrable, meters-high walls to subtle differentiations of space, a similar result of spatial isolation and discouragement of public activity or urban spontaneity can be achieved across cases. While the impacts of such urban gating have only recently received scholarly attention, we argue the spaces, whether enclosed by hard or 'soft' boundaries, cultivate (purposefully) inactive urban space.

5. Neoliberal and politicized exclusion in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

This research provides insight into how metropolitan socio-cultural conditions and national political forces interact with luxury gated development in urban Israel. While Jerusalem and Tel Aviv have experienced a boom in gated communities, they are designed to attract completely different target demographics as illustrated by their marketing material, architectural design, and the role of security versus prestige. Jerusalem, a religious city and central to global Jewry's heritage and national consciousness, has witnessed an increase in gated development that emphasizes its nationalistic and historical character, and caters to a wealthy and religious class of transnational and mobile Jewish migrants seeking an ethno- or religio-national home that fulfills an imagined, orientalized version of the city. In contrast, the gated enclaves of Tel Aviv conform to a different version (and means of attainment) of the Zionist dream: aesthetically globalized, ultra-modern high-rise towers, presented as simultaneously embedded within the city's cosmopolitanism and detached from its chaos, while serving an investment, or 'business-oriented,' function as a real estate product that enriches the economy of a recently self-proclaimed Jewish nation state (BBC, 2018). Techniques of exclusion or discouraging access, however, can be described as generally similar across the metropolitan areas.

We demonstrate firstly that urban gated communities, and exclusionary urban development more generally, are influenced by elite preferences and socio-cultural conditions on the intra- and trans-national scales (Yip, 2012; Wissink, 2013). In the context of deepening (and creeping) neoliberalism and privatization of urban space,

Jerusalem's and Tel Aviv's gated enclaves are developed and marketed towards different generalized groups of potential residents. This research therefore emphasizes the specificity and heterogeneity of political-cultural meanings and transformations associated with gatedness.

Importantly, however, we have also sought to demonstrate and emphasize that, despite the varied built and social manifestations of gatedness across Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, both operate largely in accordance with economic neoliberalism and advance Israeli state goals related to geopolitical strategy and its international standing and reputation. The gated communities are geared toward seemingly opposite demographics, yet each are envisioned as playing a role in strengthening Israeli legitimacy, its geopolitical/security situation, and/or its economic prowess.

The cities, then, represent quite different experiences with navigating globalization and managing neoliberalism on the municipal level, yet both advance similar national interests—contributing to and reflecting a national-level gatedness of regional detachment. Patterns of development in both cities, seen through the different forms and marketing of gated developments, are politicized and sanctioned by the state, evident, for example, in the generous tax incentives for foreign buyers in Jerusalem or the cultivated detachment from political issues in Tel Aviv. This represents a convergence of neoliberal economic and religio-national agendas. As Cohen-Hattab (2004: 78) writes in relation to the role of foreign visits and tourism in the pre-State mandatory period, 'the Zionists believed that tourism offered them an opportunity to promote the Jewish national endeavor and influence world public opinion in their favor.' Such promotional aims, referred to as a 'political-propaganda tool' (Cohen-Hattab, 2004: 78), did not cease after the creation of the State of Israel, the author notes.

Our research bolsters the similar notion of a so-called 'ethnic logic', conceptualized by scholars like Tzfadia (2005) and Yacobi (2012a, 2012b), that underpins urban development and forms the basis of the 'gating machine' (La Grange, 2014; Vesselinov, Cazessus and Falk, 2007) in Israel—including both Jerusalem and Tel Aviv. The importance of social characteristics (especially the Jewish/Palestinian cleavage) in organizing Israeli spatial planning and residential development is *concealed* by its deeply commanding, all-encompassing role, allowing the attribution of inequalities and exclusionary construction to principles of capitalism and neoliberalism (and not state-encouraged segregation or discrimination). And especially in the Tel Aviv context, where economic and 'enlightened' cultural activity predominates, the developments communicate an air of cosmopolitanism and legitimacy that is often confounded by the negative religious and political connotations attached to Jerusalem. Interestingly, while neoliberal interests increasingly infiltrate and shape rural gatedness (Charney and Palgi, 2018), especially in kibbutzim (which are a more established, legacy form of gatedness), contemporary dynamics of urban gated communities exhibit a growing religio-national logic, particularly in Jerusalem, in addition to neoliberal tendencies.

This study has also built on recent gated communities literature that examines how gating and exclusionary urbanism may be perpetuated in the absence of physical gates, as they are conventionally understood. To be sure, many of the gated developments discussed here do erect physical, impenetrable boundaries such as walls and fences, but as we have demonstrated in the context of Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, exclusion and gatedness may be achieved by the employment of 'softer' boundaries, such as signage, infrastructural barriers, CCTV cameras, guard posts, strategic delineations of public space, and verticality. All the more so in the Israeli context, where security concerns are often seen as superseding other needs, a theater of fortification is expected and encouraged. We therefore support the position that scholars must look 'beyond gated communities' (Bagaeen and Uduku, 2015) and develop a more nuanced definition of gatedness that accounts for the exclusionary nature of luxury condominiums and inner city developments more generally (Rosen and Walks, 2015a; Graham, 2015), in order to better understand how dynamics of power may be reproduced both explicitly

and implicitly by the state, and at a variety of scales and sites within Israel.

Considering certain forms of luxury inner city development as embodying different dimensions of urban gating has both research and policy implications. The significance of a study of 'soft boundaries' in the modern neoliberal city is that it can help reveal new forms of urban exclusion, both socioeconomic and spatial, and help detect the impacts of luxury development on social, economic, and built diversity. It challenges local planners and officials to stem the proliferation of 'secret public' (Hasson, 2016) parks and courtyards privatized or made otherwise inaccessible by adjacent luxury compounds. Gating is a heterogeneous phenomenon with diverse motivations, manifestations, and implications, shaped by both city-level conditions and national interests, as well as the global circulation of capital and ideas. Particularly in Israel, where a range of social cleavages characterize the societal structure, urban gated development interacts with politics in a particularly consequential way and serves to exacerbate, or at least perpetuate, tensions along religious, national, and class boundaries.

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References

- Alaily-Mattar, N., 2008. Beyond gated communities? Detachment and concentration in networked nodes of affluence in the city of Beirut. *Urban Des. Int.* 13 (4), 263–271.
- Alfasi, N., Fenster, T., 2005. A tale of two cities: Jerusalem and Tel Aviv in an age of globalization. *Cities* 22 (5), 351–363.
- Alfasi, N., Ganan, E., 2015. Jerusalem of (foreign) gold: Entrepreneurship and pattern-driven policy in a historic city. *Urban Geogr.* 26 (2), 157–180.
- Avni, N., Alfasi, N., Margalit, T., 2019;al., forthcoming. Tel Aviv-Jaffa: New trends, old divisions. In: Xiangming, C., Moser, S., Ratoola, K. (Eds.), *Research Handbook on Asian Cities*. Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, U.K. (forthcoming).
- Bagaeen, S., Uduku, O., 2015. *Beyond Gated Communities*. Routledge, London and New York.
- Blakely, E.J., Snyder, M.G., 1997. *Fortress America: Gated Communities in the United States*. Brookings Institution Press, Washington, D.C.
- Charney, I., Palgi, M., 2018. Varie(gated) communities: Looking into socio-spatial splintering in renewing kibbutzim. *J. Rural Stud.* 57, 36–43.
- Cohen-Hattab, K., 2004. Zionism, tourism, and the battle for Palestine. *Israel Stud.* 9 (1), 61–85.
- Csefalvay, Z., 2011. Gated communities for security or prestige? A public choice approach and the case of Budapest. *Int. J. Urban Reg. Res.* 35 (4), 735–752.
- Falah, G., 1996. Living together apart: residential segregation in mixed Arab-Jewish cities in Israel. *Urban Stud.* 33 (6), 823–857.
- Gadecki, J., Smigiel, C., 2013. A paradise behind gates and walls: Gated communities in Eastern Europe and the promise of happiness. In: Bartetzky, A., Schalenberg, M. (Eds.), *Urban Planning and the Pursuit of Happiness: European Variations on a Universal Theme (18th-21st centuries)*. Jovis Diskurs, Berlin.
- Genis, S., 2007. Producing elite localities: the rise of gated communities in Istanbul. *Urban Stud.* 44 (4), 771–798.
- Graham, S., 2015. Luxified skies. *City* 19 (5), 618–645.
- Grant, J., Mittelsteadt, L., 2004. Types of gated communities. *Environ. Plann. B: Plann. Des.* 31 (6), 913–930.
- Haramati, T., Hananel, R., 2016. Is anybody home? The influence of ghost apartments on urban diversity in Tel-Aviv and Jerusalem. *Cities* 56, 109–118.
- Havermans, D., Smeets, J., 2010. Gated communities: A theoretical discussion on place attachment and identity, presented at the 22nd International Housing Research Conference, Istanbul, 2–7 July.
- Kellerman, A., 1993. *Society and Settlement: Jewish Land of Israel in the Twentieth Century*. State University of New York Press, Albany.
- Khazzoom, A., 2003. The great chain of Orientalism: Jewish identity, stigma management, and ethnic exclusion in Israel. *Am. Sociol. Rev.* 68 (4), 481–510.
- Khazzoom, A., 2005. Did the Israeli state engineer segregation? On the placement of Jewish immigrants in development towns in the 1950s. *Soc. Forces* 84 (1), 115–134.

- Kipnis, B.A., 1997. Dynamics and potentials of Israel's megalopolitan processes. *Urban Stud.* 34 (3), 589–601.
- Kipnis, B.A., 2004. Tel Aviv, Israel – a world city in evolution: Urban development at a deadend of the global economy. *Dela* 21, 183–193.
- Kovacs, Z., Hegedus, G., 2014. Gated communities as new forms of segregation in post-socialist Budapest. *Cities* 36, 200–209.
- Kuppinger, P., 2004. Exclusive greenery: new gated communities in Cairo. *City Soc.* 16 (2), 35–62.
- La Grange, A., 2014. Hong Kong's gating machine. *Housing Stud.* 29 (2), 251–269.
- Landman, K., 2004. Gated communities in South Africa: the challenge for spatial planning and land use management. *Town Plann. Rev.* 75 (2), 151–172.
- Landman, K., Schonteich, M., 2002. Urban fortresses: Gated communities as a reaction to crime. *Afr. Security Rev.* 11 (4), 71–85.
- Le Goix, R., Webster, G., 2006. Gated communities, sustainable cities and a tragedy of the urban commons. *Crit. Plann.* 13, 41–64.
- Leisch, H., 2002. Gated communities in Indonesia. *Cities* 19 (5), 341–350.
- Libertun de Duren, N., 2006. Planning à la Carte: the location patterns of gated communities around Buenos Aires in a decentralized planning context. *Int. J. Urban Reg. Res.* 30 (2), 308–327.
- Low, S., 1997. Urban fear: Building the fortress city. *City Soc.* 9 (1), 53–71.
- Low, S., 2003. *Behind the Gates: Security and the Pursuit of Happiness in Fortress America*. Routledge, New York and London.
- Margalit, T., 2013. Land, politics and high-rise planning: ongoing development practices in Tel Aviv-Yafo. *Plann. Perspect.* 28 (3), 373–397.
- Margalit, T., 2014. Multi-spot-zoning: a chain of public-private development ventures in Tel Aviv. *Cities* 37, 73–81.
- Marom, N., 2014. Relating a city's history and geography with Bourdieu: One hundred years of spatial distinction in Tel Aviv. *Int. J. Urban Reg. Res.* 38 (4), 1344–1362.
- Monterescu, D., 2015. *Jaffa Shared and Shattered: Contrived Coexistence in Israel/Palestine*. Indiana University Press, Bloomington, IN.
- Mycoo, M., 2006. The retreat of the upper and middle classes to gated communities in the poststructural adjustment era: the case of Trinidad. *Environ. Plann. A* 38 (1), 131–148.
- Omer, I., Goldblatt, R., 2012. Urban spatial configuration and socio-economic residential differentiation: the case of Tel Aviv. *Comput. Environ. Urban Syst.* 36 (2), 177–185.
- Pow, C.P., 2015. Urban dystopia and epistemologies of hope. *Prog. Hum. Geogr.* 39 (4), 464–485.
- Rosen, G., Charney, I., 2016. Divided we rise: Politics, architecture and vertical cityscapes at opposite ends of Jerusalem. *Trans. Inst. Br. Geogr.* 41 (2), 163–174.
- Rosen, G., Razin, E., 2008. Enclosed residential neighborhoods in Israel: from landscapes of heritage and frontier enclaves to new gated communities. *Environ. Plann. A* 40, 1895–2913.
- Rosen, G., Razin, E., 2009. The rise of gated communities in Israel: reflections on changing urban governance in a neo-liberal era. *Urban Stud.* 46 (8), 1702–1722.
- Rosen, G., Walks, A., 2015a. Castles in Toronto's sky: Condoism as urban transformation. *J. Urban Affairs* 85 (1), 39–66.
- Rosen, G., Walks, A., 2015b. Beyond gating: Condo-ism as a way of urban life. In: Bagaee, S., Uduku, O. (Eds.), *Beyond Gated Communities*. Routledge, London and New York.
- Ruiu, M.L., 2014. Differences between cohousing and gated communities: a literature review. *Sociol. Inquiry* 84 (2), 316–335.
- Salcedo, R., Torres, A., 2004. Gated communities in Santiago: Wall or frontier? *Int. J. Urban Reg. Res.* 28 (1), 27–44.
- Santos Cruz, S., Pinho, P., 2009. Closed condominiums as urban fragments of the contemporary city. *Eur. Plann. Stud.* 17 (11), 1685–1710.
- Schnell, I., Benjamini, Y., 2004. Ethnic segregation in Tel Aviv. *Dela* 21, 445–460.
- Shahar, N., 2012. *Luxury residential towers as gated communities: The case of Tel Aviv*. Unpublished master's thesis, Technion – Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa, Israel.
- Shoshana, A., Samimian-Darash, L., 2014. Governing heterogeneous populations: 'Separate and unequal' in Israel. *Sociology* 48 (6), 1139–1155.
- Shoval, N., Cohen-Hattab, K., 2001. Urban hotel development patterns in the face of political shifts. *Ann. Tourism Res.* 28 (4), 908–925.
- Tedong, P.A., Grant, J., Azriyati, W.N., Aziz, W.A., 2015. Governing enclosure: The role of governance in producing gated communities and guarded neighborhoods in Malaysia. *Int. J. Urban Reg. Res.* 39 (1), 112–128.
- Thompson, C., 2013. Master-planned estates: privatization, socio-spatial polarization and community. *Geogr. Compass* 7 (1), 85–93.
- Tzfadia, E., 2005. The ethno-class trajectory of new neighborhoods in Israel. *GeoJournal* 64 (2), 141–151.
- Tzfadia, E., 2006. Public housing as control: spatial policy of settling immigrants in Israeli development towns. *Housing Stud.* 21 (4), 523–537.
- Vesselinov, E., 2010. Gated communities in the United States: from case studies to systematic evidence. *Sociol. Compass* 4 (11), 989–998.
- Vesselinov, E., 2012. Segregation by design: mechanisms of selection of Latinos and whites into gated communities. *Urban Affairs Review* 48 (3), 417–454.
- Vesselinov, E., Cazessus, M., Falk, W., 2007. Gated communities and spatial inequality. *J. Urban Affairs* 29 (2), 109–127.
- Webster, C., Glasze, G., Frantz, K., 2002. The global spread of gated communities. *Environ. Plann. B: Plann. Des.* 29 (3), 315–320.
- Wissink, W.L., 2013. Enclave urbanism in Mumbai: an actor-network-theory analysis of urban (dis)connection. *Geoforum* 47, 1–11.
- Yacobi, H., 2011. *Glocal Jerusalem. Conflict in Cities Annual Report*. The University of Cambridge Centre for Urban Conflicts Research, Cambridge, UK.
- Yacobi, H., 2002. The architecture of ethnic logic: exploring the meaning of the built environment in the 'mixed' city of Lod – Israel. *Geogr. Ann. Ser. B: Hum. Geogr.* 84 (3 & 4), 171–187.
- Yacobi, H., 2012a. God, globalization and geopolitics: on West Jerusalem's gated communities. *Environ. Plann. A* 44 (11), 2705–2720.
- Yacobi, H., 2012b. Borders, boundaries and frontiers: notes on Jerusalem's present geopolitics. *Eurasia Border Rev.* 3 (2), 55–69.
- Yiftachel, O., 1999. Ethnocracy: the politics of Judaizing Israel/Palestine. *Constellations* 6 (3), 364–390.
- Yiftachel, O., 2000. Social control, urban planning and ethno-class relations: Mizrahi Jews in Israel's 'development towns'. *Int. J. Urban Reg. Res.* 24 (2), 418–438.
- Yip, N.M., 2012. Walled without gates: gated communities in Shanghai. *Urban Geogr.* 33 (2), 221–236.
- Zaban, H., 2017. City of go(l)d: spatial and cultural effects of high-status Jewish immigration from Western countries on the Baka neighbourhood of Jerusalem. *Urban Stud.* 54 (7), 1539–1558.
- Zhao, P., 2013. The impact of urban sprawl on social segregation in Beijing and a limited role for spatial planning. *Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie* 104 (5), 571–587.

Web Links

- AFI Group, n.d. Savyoney Ramat Aviv: An Island of Tranquility in Tel Aviv. Retrieved from <http://res.afi-g.com/en/CompletedProjects/SavyoneyRamatAviv/pages/default.aspx> (accessed 2 December 2016).
- BBC, 2018, July 10. Jewish nation state: Israel approves controversial bill. BBC. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-44881554> (accessed 25 July 2018).
- Berggruen Residential Ltd., 2016. Meier – Security. Retrieved from www.meier.co.il/security (accessed 7 September 2017).
- David's Village, n.d. Apartment rentals in David's Village. Retrieved from <http://www.kingdavid-residence.com/apartments-category/david-village> (accessed 2 December 2016).
- Habas, n.d. 1 Rothschild Boulevard. Retrieved from <http://www.habas.com/#/israeli-activities/one-rothschild-boulevard> (accessed 2 December 2016).
- Habas, 2017. YOO Tel Aviv. Retrieved from <http://www.habas.com/#/israeli-activities/yoo-tel-aviv> (accessed 7 January 2017).
- Hanevi'im 45, 2012. Hanevi'im 45 project – Jerusalem [video]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OSokKpu9sHE> (accessed 9 January 2017).
- Hasson, N., 2016, December 31. Discovering Jerusalem's secret public gardens. Ha'aretz. Retrieved from <http://www.haaretz.com/israel-news/.premium-1.762081> (accessed 7 January 2017).
- Home Land Realty, 2009. ONE TOWER – TEL AVIV [video]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WxyjZEFB-GA> (accessed 1 March 2017).
- King David's Crown, 2013. Amenities. Retrieved from <http://www.king-david-crown.com/amenities.asp> (accessed 15 January 2017).
- Mayor of Jerusalem, 2009, December. Something good is happening in Jerusalem! Retrieved from [https://uploaded8.jerusalem.muni.il/Blogs/1_29_29_725_ENG_LETTER_B\[1\].pdf](https://uploaded8.jerusalem.muni.il/Blogs/1_29_29_725_ENG_LETTER_B[1].pdf).
- Rosenblum, K., 2013, July 22. The 'starchitect' on Tel Aviv's skyline. Ha'aretz. Retrieved from <http://www.haaretz.com/israel-news/culture/.premium-1.537215> (accessed 25 July 2018).